

Copper(II) complexes with twelve to fourteen membered ring macrocyclic ligands^ψ

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Manuscript received 6 June 2005

Copper(II) complexes of general composition Cu(L)X_2 [where L = 3,9-diethyl-2,10-dimethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene (DSL_B); 2,9-diethyl-2,10-dimethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraaza-5,6:11,12-dibenzotricyclo[2,4,4]dodeca-1,3,7,9-tetraene (DSL_C); 3,8-diethyl-2,6,9,11-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododeca-1,3,7,9-tetraene (DSL_D); X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, ½SO₄²⁻] have been synthesized. The complexes have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies. The complexes were found to stabilize tetragonal geometry except Cu(L)SO₄ which is of a five coordinate square pyramidal geometry.

Macrocyclic complexes are often prepared with the aid of metal ions as templates to direct the steric course of condensation reaction which ends with ring closure^{1,2}. In the development of new synthetic macrocyclic ligands, condensation reactions between dicarbonyl compounds and diprimary amines have played an important role³⁻⁵. In the present paper we report the synthesis and characterization of three series of Cu²⁺ complexes derived from the ligands 3,9-diethyl-2,10-dimethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene (DSL_B); 2,9-diethyl-2,10-dimethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraaza-5,6:11,12-dibenzotricyclo[2,4,4]dodeca-1,3,7,9-tetraene (DSL_C); 3,8-diethyl-2,6,9,11-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododeca-1,3,7,9-tetraene (DSL_D) (Figs. 1-3).

Results and discussion

On the basis of elemental analyses data (Table 1) all the complexes have the general compositions Cu(L)X₂ [where L = DSL_B, DSL_C, DSL_D; X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, ½SO₄²⁻]. The molar conductance measurements in DMSO show that the complexes are non-electrolytes in nature, thus indicating that the anions are coordinated to the metal ion in these complexes. So [Cu(L)X₂] formula may be suggested for these complexes.

The magnetic moments of the complexes at room temperature lie in the range 1.92-2.00 B.M., corresponding to one unpaired electron (Table 2). All the complexes may be considered to have tetragonal geometry except

the sulphato complexes which possess square-pyramidal geometry around the Cu²⁺ ion and the anions occupying the axial positions.

(A) [Cu(L)X₂] (X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻) :

On the basis of IR spectra we conclude that the ligand is tetracoordinated, through four nitrogen atoms. In the spectra of the complexes no bands were obtained for the free >C=O or primary diammines, indicating that complete condensation had occurred. The IR spectra of the nitrate complexes^{6,7} exhibits bands at ~1250, ~1020 and 858 cm⁻¹, which are consistent with the monodentate coordination of this group. The electronic spectra of six coordinate Cu²⁺ complexes have either D_{4h} or C_{4v} symmetry, and the E_g and T_{2g} levels of the ^{2D} free ion will split into B_{1g}, A_{1g}, B_{2g} and E_g levels respectively. Thus, three spin-allowed transitions are expected, in the visible and near-IR region, but only a few complexes are known⁸ in which such bands are resolved either by "Gaussian Analyses" or by "Single Crystal Polarisation" studies. These bands have been assigned to the following transitions in order of increasing energy : ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} (d_{x²-y²} → d_{z²}), ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} (d_{x²-y²} → d_{xy}) and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g (d_{x²-y²} → d_{xy,yz}). The energy level sequence will depend on the amount of tetragonal distortion due to ligand-field and the Jahn-Teller effect⁹⁻¹². The electronic spectra of chloro and nitrate complexes reported here show two characteristic bands at 10929-14858 and 19157-23041

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

Table 1. Elemental analysis, colour, molar conductance and composition of the complexes

Complex	Yield (%)	Colour	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	% Calcd. (Found)			
				C	H	N	Cu
[Cu(DSLB)Cl ₂]	77	Black	15.5	46.77 (46.89)	6.87 (6.99)	13.64 (13.69)	13.21 (13.32)
CuC ₁₆ H ₂₈ N ₂₄ Cl ₂							
[Cu(DSLC)Cl ₂]	65	Green	14.3	55.18 (55.32)	5.05 (5.13)	11.70 (11.82)	13.27 (13.31)
CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ Cl ₂							
[Cu(DSLD)Cl ₂]	62	Brown	12.8	46.79 (46.92)	6.86 (6.96)	13.62 (13.69)	15.44 (15.55)
CuC ₁₈ H ₂₈ N ₄ Cl ₂							
[Cu(DSLB)(NO ₃) ₂]	70	Black	15.4	41.42 (41.61)	6.08 (6.12)	18.11 (18.24)	13.70 (13.91)
CuC ₁₆ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₆							
[Cu(DSLC)(NO ₃) ₂]	58	Black	14.7	49.67 (49.76)	4.55 (4.66)	15.80 (15.94)	11.94 (12.08)
CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆							
[Cu(DSLD)(NO ₃) ₂]	72	Green	16.8	41.44 (41.56)	6.07 (6.14)	18.13 (18.22)	13.72 (13.85)
CuC ₁₈ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₆							
[Cu(DSLB)SO ₄]	64	Brown	11.2	47.43 (47.53)	6.47 (6.56)	12.85 (13.01)	14.57 (14.61)
CuC ₁₆ H ₂₈ N ₄ SO ₄							
[Cu(DSLC)SO ₄]	70	Green	16.6	52.42 (52.56)	4.80 (4.92)	11.12 (11.18)	12.60 (12.68)
CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ SO ₄							
[Cu(DSLD)SO ₄]	68	Black	15.4	44.07 (44.15)	6.46 (6.42)	12.87 (12.98)	14.57 (14.72)
CuC ₁₈ H ₂₈ N ₄ SO ₄							

Table 2. Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1}) and magnetic moments (B.M.)

Complex	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
[Cu(DSLB)Cl ₂]	14858, 23041	1.92
[Cu(DSLC)Cl ₂]	11614, 19230	1.98
[Cu(DSLD)Cl ₂]	10929, 23041	1.94
[Cu(DSLB)(NO ₃) ₂]	14492, 20500	1.96
[Cu(DSLC)(NO ₃) ₂]	14368, 22800	1.92
[Cu(DSLD)(NO ₃) ₂]	14500, 19157	1.92
[Cu(DSLB)SO ₄]	11338, 19500	1.97
[Cu(DSLC)SO ₄]	15385, 18668	1.94
[Cu(DSLD)SO ₄]	14815, 21800	2.00

cm^{-1} . These bands may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively. The ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transition is usually not observed as a separate band in the tetragonal field. The splitting of the 2E_g state is a measure of planar and axial field. Since planar field is constant in all the present complexes, the change in the bands should be due to axial field only. The complexes exhibit an anisotropic EPR spectra characteristic of tetragonal geometry for copper(II). The observed g values are reported in Table 3. The anisotropic g -values have been calculated by Kneubuhl's methods¹³ and by methods re-

ported earlier^{13,14}. $G = (g_{||} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$, which measures the exchange interaction between the copper centers in polycrystalline samples, have been calculated. According to Hathaway^{11,12}, if $G > 4$, the exchange interaction is negligible. A value of $G < 4$, indicates considerable exchange interaction in solid complexes. The calculated G values are presented in Table 3 and larger than 4, suggesting that there is no interaction between the copper centers.

(B) Cu(L)SO_4 :

Infrared spectra⁵ of these complexes show monodentate behaviour of the sulphate group. A five coordinate structure is thus readily suggested for these complexes. Two basic structures¹⁵ can be adopted by complex compounds

Table 3. ESR spectral data of copper(II) complexes

Complex	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	g_{iso}	G
[Cu(DSLB)Cl ₂]	2.27	2.06	2.13	4.79
[Cu(DSLC)Cl ₂]	2.26	2.05	2.12	5.15
[Cu(DSLD)Cl ₂]	2.28	2.05	2.14	4.76
[Cu(DSLB)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.27	2.07	2.13	4.15
[Cu(DSLC)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.26	2.05	2.13	4.64
[Cu(DSLD)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.26	2.06	2.10	4.56

for coordination number five, i.e. trigonal bipyramidal and square pyramidal, which are characterized by the ground states $d_{x^2-y^2}$ or d_{z^2} respectively^{16,17}. EPR spectra of these complexes provide an excellent basis for distinguishing between these two ground states. For system with $g_3 > g_2 > g_1$ the ratio¹⁹ $(g_2 - g_1)/(g_3 - g_2)$ called the parameter R , is very useful for this purpose. If the ground state is predominantly, d_{z^2} , the value of R is greater than one. On the other hand, for the ground state predominantly $d_{x^2-y^2}$, the value of R is less than one. All the sulphato complexes give EPR spectra showing three g -values. The value of g_1 , g_2 , g_3 and R are presented in Table 4. The calculated values of R for sulphato complexes indicate a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state, which is consistent with a square pyramidal geometry, Fig. 3(a-c). The electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit bands in the range 11338–15385 and 18668–21800 cm^{-1} ^{18,19}. These data are comparable with square pyramidal geometry²⁰. Thus for the Cu(L)SO_4 , a five coordinate square pyramidal geometry may be proposed.

Table 4. ESR spectral data of copper(II) sulphato complexes

Complex	g_3	g_2	g_1	g_{iso}	R
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DSL B})\text{SO}_4]$	2.503	2.164	2.057	2.241	0.316
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DSL C})\text{SO}_4]$	2.217	2.116	2.087	2.101	0.333
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DSL D})\text{SO}_4]$	2.134	2.092	2.078	2.140	0.287

On the basis of the above spectral studies the following structures (Figs. 4–9) are suggested to the present complexes under study.

Experimental

Preparation of the complexes :

A template reaction was carried out for the formation of the complexes. A hot ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the respective copper(II) salt (0.025 mol) was mixed with a hot ethanolic solution (20 ml) of 1,3-diaminopropane (3.70 g, 0.05 mol)/*o*-phenylenediamine (5.40 g, 0.05 mol)/1,2-diamino propane (3.70 g, 0.05 mol). Then an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of 2,3-pentanedione (5.0 g, 0.05 mol) in the presence of an ethanolic lithium hydroxide solution (0.042 g, 0.01 mol) was added to the resultant solution with stirring. This solution was refluxed for 8 h. On cooling, a coloured complex precipitated out. The complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol, and dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} .

Physical measurements :

Spectroscopic grade DMSO was used for the spectral and molar conductance studies. The C, H and N data

Fig. 1. DSLB

Fig. 2. DSLC

Fig. 3. DSLD

$X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{NO}_3^-$

Fig. 4

$X = \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_3$

Fig. 5

$X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{NO}_3^-$

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

were obtained using a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer and are reported in Table 1. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 instrument as nujol mull/KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on a Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. Molar conductances were measured on an ELICO conductivity bridge (Type CM 82T). Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance at room temperature, using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant. EPR spectra of all the complexes were recorded on powder samples, at room temperature, on an E_4 -EPR spectrometer using the DPPH as the *g*-marker.

Acknowledgement

We thank the Principal, Zakir Husain College, Delhi University, Delhi, for providing laboratory facilities and to the R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Mumbai for recording the EPR spectra and DRDO, New Delhi for financial assistance.

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